

Gender STI

D5.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CAPES: Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior

CNPq: Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico

CONICYT: Comisión Nacional de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica

EC DG RTD: European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

EFFORTI: Evaluation Framework for Promoting Gender Equality in Research and Innovation

ERA: European Research Area

EU MS and AC: European Union Member States and Associated Countries

GEARING Roles: Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to traNsform Gender ROLES

GEECCO: Gender Equality in Engineering through Communication and Commitment

GENDER-NET Plus: ERA-NET Cofund Promoting Gender Equality in H2020 and the ERA

GENDERACTION: GENDER equality in the ERA Community To Innovate policy implementatiON

MINCYT: Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación

NCPs: National Contact Points

NSF: National Science Foundation

RPOs: Research Performing Organizations

RTOS: Research and Technology Organizations

S&T: Science and Technology

SFIC: Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation

RFOs: Research Funding Organizations

STI: Science, Technology and Innovation

SwafS: Science with and for Society

SWG GRI: Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation

TARGET: TAKing a Reflexive approach to Gender Equality for institutional Transformation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the GENDER STI Communication and Dissemination Plan, which is composed of the project's communication and dissemination strategies and actions. This set of measures aims to increase the project's overall impact by introducing it to its key target audiences in Europe and selected third countries; create a deeper understanding of the project and its objectives; promote the project to raise awareness about it with key stakeholders; create synergies with ERA-related groups and other EU-funded initiatives; and transfer knowledge generated by the project to stakeholder groups that can benefit from and exploit the information.

The project's plan aims to achieve success by executing a unique strategy for communication and another for dissemination. Although these elements are described separately in the plan, certain activities are closely linked. The plan is a living document, which will be continuously adapted and updated as needed to maximize the project's impact.

The project's target audiences are a critical part of the GENDER STI Communication and Dissemination Plan, and the consortium has crafted the plans with these specific audiences in mind. In addition, the plan will include an estimated execution timeline.

The GENDER STI Communication and Dissemination Plan is divided into six sections.

- **Chapter 1: Project Objectives:** This chapter will describe the plan's communication and dissemination objectives.
- **Chapter 2: Target Audiences.** This chapter will describe the project's target audiences, which are critical to the plan and will be paramount to promoting gender equality in science, technology and innovation.
- **Chapter 3: Communication Strategy.** This chapter will describe the project's communication strategy, which is designed to promote the project and its results throughout its lifetime.
- **Chapter 4: Dissemination STRATEGY.** This chapter will describe the project's dissemination strategy, which is designed to transfer knowledge created by the project to parties that can benefit from and exploit the results.
- **Chapter 5: Estimated Execution Timeline.** This chapter will provide estimated dates for planned project communication and dissemination actions.
- **Chapter 6: Key Performance Indicators.** This chapter will describe the project's key performance indicators (KPIs), which will allow the consortium to measure the plan's effectiveness in a quantitative and qualitative manner.

Main results from the GENDER STI Communication and Dissemination Plan will be reported in D5.2 Communication and Dissemination Mid-term Report and D5.3 Communication and Dissemination Final Report. These deliverables will also include a description of the main events organized by the project and the third-party events attended by the partners during the reporting periods.

1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

GENDER STI is a Research and Innovation Action that aims to analyze how gender equality matters are taken into consideration at different levels of international cooperation dialogues in the area of science, technology and innovation (STI). To do this, it will work with 10 third countries from three continents and analyze bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI between EU Member States and Associated Countries with these countries.

As established by the European Commission, **communication** in Horizon 2020 projects refers to a “strategically planned process” aimed at promoting the action and its results throughout the project’s lifetime.¹ One of the aims of this is to show the impact and benefits of EU-funded research and innovation activities. Meanwhile, **dissemination** refers to the transfer of project-generated knowledge and results to audiences that can use the results.

Although these activities sometimes overlap, they serve different purposes. As such, the objectives for each strategy vary, but they are meant to work in harmony. A strong communication strategy will help the project become known among GENDER STI’s target audiences, thereby increasing its possibilities at disseminating generated knowledge and results in the future. On the other hand, a strong dissemination strategy will highlight the important work being carried out by the project and demonstrate the enrichment created by EU-funded projects. Together, communication and dissemination create the groundwork for exploitation and sustainability, which will be discussed in detail in D5.6 – Exploitation Plan, due in M36.

1.1 Communication Objectives

The project aims to use communication to inform its target groups about how gender equality is taken into consideration at different levels of international cooperation dialogues in the area of STI. Thus, communication objectives are focused on

¹ Scherer, J., & Weber, S., et al. (2018). *Making the Most of Your H2020 Project: Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.* https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

introducing the project, fomenting a deeper understanding of it and consistently promoting it through its lifetime.

- **Introduce the project to GENDER STI's target audiences:** A successful introduction to the right groups is crucial to build momentum for the project. This will lay the groundwork for future communication about GENDER STI's progress and results.
- **Create a deeper understanding of the GENDER STI project and its objectives:** Communication measures work to create a deeper understanding of the project. Developing this understanding will be beneficial when the project disseminates project results as stakeholders will be able to clearly identify why GENDER STI project outcomes are relevant to them or their work.
- **Promote GENDER STI and raise awareness about it:** Promoting GENDER STI and raising awareness about the importance of investigating the state of gender equality in STI dialogues with third countries is crucial. This will help the project sustain momentum, ensuring that target groups are aware of the project throughout its lifetime and beyond.

1.2 Dissemination Objectives

By disseminating project results to specific target audiences, GENDER STI aims to create a cascade effect, thereby maximizing the project's reach. Employing the cascade approach means that GENDER STI is also working to make the project results sustainable after its conclusion. The following are the project's dissemination objectives.

- **Transfer GENDER STI knowledge and outcomes to stakeholder groups that can use the information:** GENDER STI will disseminate project results to relevant stakeholder groups, including STI policy makers in Europe and in third countries, the gender research community and NCP networks, among many others, to expand knowledge on the state of gender equality in bilateral and multilateral STI dialogues. This will allow groups to use GENDER STI results to inform their positions in STI dialogues, offer advice to policy makers, complement their gender investigations or initiatives and stimulate new research questions on this topic.
- **Create synergies with ERA-related groups.** GENDER STI will establish synergies with the two primary ERA groups on gender equality and international cooperation: the SWG GRI and the SFIC. GENDER STI will disseminate project results to the ERA groups and establish a dynamic two-way communication channel with them to guide future project actions.
- **Create synergies with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, in particular with SwafS projects:** As soon as the first GENDER STI results are available, the project will disseminate the results to related EU-funded projects, including GENDERACTION and GENDER-NET Plus partners.
- **Engage with key stakeholder groups to obtain feedback on project results:** The engagement aspect of the project, which is characterized by the creation of a two-way communication channel between GENDER STI and target stakeholder groups, is an important part of dissemination. It ensures that GENDER STI project results are discussed and considered for future initiatives and allows the consortium to consider comments and feedback from outside experts.

2 TARGET AUDIENCES

As mentioned above, it is important to tailor the project's communication and dissemination strategies to specific target audiences. This focused approach will ensure that information about GENDER STI gets to the right people: those who will be interested in the results and are open to possibly using them in the future.

GENDER STI's communication and dissemination efforts will focus on the following target groups. This targeting will define the tone, wording and content produced by the project.

- **STI policy makers in the EU, MS, AC and third countries:** On one side, this group includes policy makers, e.g., the EC DG RTD and REA, government bodies and institutions focused on gender issues in EU MS and AC. It also encompasses key stakeholders and actors involved in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements with third countries, such as Ministries of Foreign Affairs, Research Funding Organizations (RFOs), international cooperation agencies, etc. On the other, this group includes policy makers from the third countries that participate as partners in the consortium, such as ministries of science and technology and funding agencies. For instance, the GENDER STI consortium involves the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), one of Canada's federal granting councils for research. In addition, funding agencies from Brazil (CNPq and CAPES) will join the Advisory Board. Furthermore, the consortium has established collaboration relationships with other funding agencies, like NSF (US) and CONICYT (Chile), and S&T Ministries like MINCYT (Argentina) and policy makers that can be effectively reached to disseminate relevant project outcomes.
- **Scientific and research community:** The scientific and research community involves research and scientific organizations, RPOs, such as the Mission for the Place of Women at CNRS, and RTOs, including researchers in EU-funded projects as well as national projects and initiatives. Examples of such projects that focus on gender equality are GENDER-NET Plus and SwafS projects such as GENDERACTION, TARGET, EFFORTI, GEECCO and GEARING Roles, among others. The consortium is well connected to the partners from these projects, some of them will be in the Advisory Board, and will be able to effectively disseminate information and collect their feedback on GENDER STI activities.
- **ERA-related groups on gender equality in STI and international cooperation:** These groups are an important target given that they often provide valuable information to policy making bodies and governments. These groups include the Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (SWG GRI), which advises the Council of the EU and the EC on policies and initiatives on gender equality, and the Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation (SFIC), which oversees the sharing and structuring information on S&T cooperation and pooling relevant knowledge on third countries, among others. The GENDER STI consortium maintains a constant dialogue with members of such working groups and envisages a close collaboration during the project lifecycle.
- **NCP networks in the EU and in third country partners:** GENDER STI will also target the National Contact Points for H2020 and Horizon Europe in EU and third country partners. We will focus on the Net4Society group, the international network of NCPs for Societal Challenge 6 and social sciences, and IDEAL-IST, the international ICT NCP network. Moreover, GENDER STI

benefits from the presence of NCPs in three of the third country partners: the Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey (Mexico), the Universidade de São Paulo (Brazil) and the Euro-India Research Centre (India). All NCPs in the consortium believe strongly in the need to promote gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements and international cooperation in STI. We will introduce the project to the NCP networks, keeping them informed of its progress in order to create awareness of GENDER STI research.

- **Industry leaders and innovators:** The industry is a critical target for the GENDER STI project given the role it plays in establishing excellence and norms in science and technology. This group includes leaders at private technology companies, entrepreneurs, startups, think tanks, innovators and more. GENDER STI consortium has close ties to industry leaders working in STI. The consortium has first-hand knowledge of the importance of gender equality to many stakeholders in the private sector and will work closely with the industry to inform key stakeholders of the project's advancements.
- **NGOs, agencies, associations, visionary individuals and organizations that advocate for higher R&I quality through gender equality:** Finally, the GENDER STI project will target the organizations in this group, which focus on gender equality in science and technology. These entities, such as consortium partners Red Argentina de Género, Ciencia y Tecnología and the Gender Equality and Affirmative Action Office at TU Graz, play an important role in educating the public and private sectors about striving for and implementing gender equality. The GENDER STI consortium have interacted with members in this group via various initiatives and thus have easy access to them.

3 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

GENDER STI's communication plan is built on three pillars: launch and connect, build momentum, and cascade to increase reach. Together, all three initiatives work in synergy to maximize project visibility and penetration. The communication plan also provides the necessary support for GENDER STI to execute its dissemination strategy and plan.

Launch and connect: The project website and social media channels have been launched. It then works to introduce GENDER STI and explain its objectives in relevant stakeholder communities via the consortium's professional and institutional networks.

Build momentum: After establishing the project, it is important to build momentum and maintain it by promoting the first project results on mapping gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements in the STI area between the EU MS and AC and the 10 selected third countries. This will depend on how the research is progressing and can be modified as needed. The consortium will promote conferences and events aimed at presenting the interim results.

Cascade to increase reach: The final aspect of GENDER STI's communication plan focuses on creating a communication cascade, a process by which key actors pass along GENDER STI content and results to other key actors, ensuring maximum reach and impact. This will include reaching out to specialized and general media and launching email, social media and web campaigns so that GENDER STI followers can share project results.

3.1 Communication Channels

GENDER STI's communication channels will help promote the project and create an understanding of its work. The following channels will position GENDER STI as a cutting-edge Horizon 2020 project analyzing a fundamental aspect of our society: the role of gender equality in STI in bilateral and multilateral dialogues between MS and AC in some of the most prominent and influential countries in the world. This positioning will ensure that stakeholders perceive GENDER STI as an exciting top-of-mind project. These channels will be used to promote the project upon launch and will remain active during and after GENDER STI's conclusion.

3.1.1 Website

GENDER STI's central communication channel is its website (www.gender-sti.org), which will establish its online presence. The website has been implemented using a web platform and supported by a top-notch content management system and web publisher. The website will inform key stakeholders about the project and its scope as well as keep target groups up to date on the progress of GENDER STI's research.

An excerpt of the project's website is featured below.

Website Homepage

The website homepage has been designed as a dynamic and informative landing page that provides visitors with a main overview of the project in one place. It allows users to connect directly with the project and also informs them of the latest project news and activities. The project's one-of-a-kind consortium is featured on the homepage and a related link allows interested visitors to learn more about the project. Visitors are provided with a quick way to contact the project and also informed that the website complies with the General Data Protection Regulation's requirements.

Project relevance in the covid-19 era

The homepage immediately tells visitors why GENDER STI is relevant in the covid-19 era. To illustrate this, it features insights from the project's partners.

Here is one example of one of the featured quotes from project partners: "It has been shown that female scientists posted fewer pre-prints and registered fewer new studies compared to their male colleagues during the pandemic... Since there is evidence that gender inequities have been exacerbated during the covid-19 pandemic, the pandemic may directly impact the participation of women in STI projects all over the world. It will be crucial for the Gender STI project to not only rigorously assess gender equality but also to put forward recommendations to enhance gender equality in the context of a pandemic and other public health crises."
– Anne-Cécile Desfaits, Canadian Institutes of Health Research

Project focus areas

The homepage also lays out the project's focus areas: gender equality in scientific careers; gender balance in decision making; and the integration of the gender dimension in R&I content.

News & Events

The News & Events section is important as it communicates that GENDER STI is an active project. This section also features the latest news on gender equality in STI, which allows it to serve as an authoritative resource for stakeholders interested in gender equality.

News & Events

[ALL CATEGORIES](#) [EVENTS](#) [NEWS](#)

22.01.2021

Gender STI Will Attend the 6th World Congress on Women in Bangalore

The Gender STI project will attend the 6th World Congress on Women in Bangalore, India on March 8.

21.12.2020

Gender STI Holds Virtual Kick-Off Meeting With Partners From Four...

While adapting activities to the realities of the covid-19 pandemic can be challenging, the Gender STI consortium has...

03.12.2020

EC's New Gender Action Plan Aims to Have 85% of...

The European Commission's Gender Action Plan III has marked an ambitious course of action to promote gender equality...

01.11.2020

News Release: International EU-Funded Consortium I launches

Consortium

A core element of the project's unique value proposition is its consortium. It brings together 18 organizations from all around the world with the same goal: promote gender equality in STI. This value and reach is reflected on the homepage.

Gender STI is a project with an international consortium from all corners of the world.

Our partners are from Spain, Finland, Portugal, Austria, France, Italy, Canada, the United States, Mexico, Brazil, Chile, Argentina, South Africa, India, South Korea and China.

[Learn more about Gender STI](#)

Connecting with the project

Visitors are given the opportunity to connect with the project on the homepage by signing up for the European Observatory on Gender in STI's newsletter. The newsletter, which is sent out once each quarter, informs users of project activities and important gender equality news, among others.

Contact

Providing a clear and easy-to-find point of contact is of paramount important for any project. This is why a contact form is included on GENDER STI’s homepage and on every single page of the website.

CONTACT US

Your name * Your phone number

Your email *

Comment

By pressing the "SEND" button you confirm that you have read, understand and accept the conditions of the Privacy Policy set out and linked located in this [LINK](#).

[Send](#)

E-mail us contact@gender-sti.org

Privacy Policy

The GENDER STI consortium is committed to ensure the protection of personal data and user privacy. The GENDER STI Privacy Policy aims to inform the public, website visitors and other stakeholders about how we process personal data, based on data protection principles, in accordance with [Articles 12, 13, and 14](#) of the GDPR.

[+ Show more](#)

Project grant number and funding statement

Our project is proud to have been selected to receive Horizon 2020 funding and we firmly believe in the power and reach of European R&I. This is reflected in the homepage footer, which discloses the project’s funding source and its grant number. This footer is included on every single page of the project’s website.

3.1.2 Social networks

Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn serve as the project’s official social media channels because of their high levels of engagement and professional nature. These channels have already been created.

Twitter Profile

Facebook Profile

LinkedIn Profile

3.1.3 Partner networks and multipliers

GENDER STI partners possess an unparalleled network of connections in STI and gender communities on an EU and international level. This powerful network will act as a unique multiplier to cascade GENDER STI objectives and results across relevant stakeholder communities.

3.1.4 Specialized and general media

The project will reach out to specialized and generalized media outlets. This will allow GENDER STI to communicate its project objectives to varied and niche groups, such as the [European Science-Media Hub](#) and [EuroNews](#).

3.1.5 Events

Project events

The project will organize a series of Co-Design Labs that will be deployed as a dynamic mix of workshops, demonstrations and guided hands-on teamwork based on design thinking principles. To get ready for the labs, all partners will undergo an internal training.

The project will also host a final project event in M36, which will serve to promote the project's overall efforts and achievements as well as to disseminate its results.

Tentative schedule of significant projects events:

Event	Tentative Date
Co-Design Lab Training 1 (Internal)	May/June 2021
Co-Design Lab Training 2 (Internal)	May/June 2021
1 st Co-Design Lab	September/October 2021
2 nd Co-Design Lab	April/May 2022
3 rd Co-Design Lab	September/October 2022
Final Project Event	October 2023

Third party events

The consortium will also participate in relevant conferences and events related to gender and international cooperation in STI. These events will allow the consortium to promote the project to target audiences. The tentative list of events that GENDER STI partners will attend virtually and in person, where possible, during the project's first reporting period is included below.

	Event	Description	Date
1	Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Virtual Summit 2021	The Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Virtual Summit is a gathering of Diversity, Equity, Equality, Inclusion, Belonging, Culture, Talent, and Human Resources practitioners, that will connect, benchmark, network, and focus on key strategies, practices, and ideas to create long-term, impactful, change during this unprecedented time in history.	4 February 2021
2	ifempower	The event will be held under the title, "How does the idea become a business? Matchmaking and knowledge exchange for business angels, female entrepreneurs and potential entrepreneurs, experts and other stakeholders." It aims to provide a platform for matchmaking and online knowledge exchange for business angels, entrepreneurs, experts and other stakeholders.	4 February 2021
3	6th World Congress on Women	The World Congress on Women features the theme, "Celebrating the Past, Planning for the Future, and designed to motivate, inspire, connect and celebrate professional women and entrepreneurs.	8 March 2021

4	IEEE Winter Summit on BHI, AI, and IR for Combating COVID19	The IEEE-EMBS-BHI (Biomedical and Health Informatics) Technical Committee organizes together with IEEE Future Directions committee the Winter Summit on BHI, AI, and IR (Intelligent Reality) for Combating COVID19. Within the summit conference, there will be a session on diversity and inclusion that will aim to promote women and under-represented-minority working in COVID19	12-17 March 2021
5	Addressing Global Challenges Together: The Role of Science Diplomacy	Hosted by Horizon 2020 project S4DC, this networking meeting aims to deconstruct the permanent and ad-hoc scientific advisory mechanisms in place to address global challenges using science diplomacy.	15-19 March 2021
6	Gender Summit: Gender Equality, Diversity, Inclusion post-Corona: Quo vadis?	The summit will convene international decision makers, policy representatives, funders, scientists and scholars from disciplines and sectors to discuss the current and emerging challenges facing science and society, and develop a more equal, inclusive, and sustainable vision of excellence in science.	14-16 April 2021
7	Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in Artificial Intelligence Workshop	Canadian and EU researchers and funding agencies will participate in this workshop to identify strategies and partnerships to advance research on EDI in AI.	26-27 April 2021
8	Congreso Iberoamericano de Ciencia, Tecnología y Género	This bi-annual conference brings together key players from Spain and Latin America and analyses STI issues from a gender perspective.	14-16 July 2021
9	Science and Technology Society Forum	The Science and Technology in Society forum aims to provide a mechanism for open discussions on an informal basis, and to build a human network that would, in time, resolve the new types of problems stemming from the application of science and technology.	2-5 October 2021
10	International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (IEEE EMBC)	The IEEE EMBS is the world's largest international biomedical engineering conference. The conference covers diverse topics of cutting edge research and innovation in biomedical engineering, healthcare technology R&D, translational clinical research, technology transfer and entrepreneurship, and biomedical engineering education.	31 October-4 November 2021
11	14th Academic International Conference on Multidisciplinary	The Academic International Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies and Education aims to provide a platform and stimulate discussion on issues surrounding education, gender studies, environmental studies,	15-17 November 2021

	Studies and Education	urban and regional studies, philosophy, social justice and sociology, business management and law in related areas	
12	EBN Congress 2021	The major annual EBN event gathers experts from all over the world. The Congress aims to encourage cooperation among EU BICs, incubators, startups and investors, helping each other grow and expand to the international market. The event focuses on sustainable technology, access to finances and international opportunities.	November 2021
13	ISERT 2021: International Conference on Interdisciplinary Studies in Education Research and Technology 2021 (ISERT 2021)	ISERT 2021 will focus on the application of the latest interdisciplinary studies to all aspects of education, research and technology. The objectives of this conference are to explore the experimental, theoretical and scientific data analysis foundations of interdisciplinary studies.	16-19 December 2021
14	38th IASP World Conference on Science Parks and Areas of Innovation 2021	IASP is the leading association of innovation ecosystems worldwide and aims to be the global network for science parks (STPs), innovation districts, knowledge cities and other areas of innovation (AOIs), driving growth, internationalization and effectiveness for members. The annual IASP World Conference is the main networking event of our association, gathering an ever-increasing number of delegates and speakers from all over the world, linking global innovation leaders and experts.	December 2021
15	RAGCyT-CONICET Monthly Conferences on Women in Science and Technology	Organized by RAGCyT, a GENDER STI partner, and CONICET, these monthly conferences focus on the perspective science and technology researchers and promotes the motivation and inclusion of women across all sectors. They also aim to analyze the role of technology and policy in our current society. The events feature senior policy makers from Argentina and other countries in Latin America.	Monthly throughout 2021.
16	Future of Work Equitable Digital Systems Forums	This IDRC-led multi-partner project focuses on inclusion in the workplace especially with regards to digital systems and related standards. Its forums will aim to identify accessibility gaps and develop a research knowledge base of current and emerging technical systems that present barriers to employees.	Throughout 2021.
17	Generation Equality Forum	The Generation Equality Forum is a civil society-driven global event to further gender equality, convened by UN Women and co-chaired by France and Mexico. After being	2021. Date TBA.

		postponed because of the covid-19 crisis, the event, which should have been held in July 2020, will take place in the first half of 2021, in Mexico City and then in Paris.	
18	EU-CELAC- Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation (JIRI) Senior Officials Meetings (SOM)	This forum brings together senior policy makers from both regions, including GENDER STI representatives (VTT, ITESM, USP) who will promote further action by the countries involved in order to include gender in the bilateral cooperation agenda.	2021. Date TBA.
19	DEEP Conference	OCAD University, a GENDER STI partner, hosts an annual DEEP Conference focuses on the inclusion of individuals across all sectors and analyses the role of technology and policy in our current society.	2021. Date TBA.
20	TICAL Conference	The TICAL Conference is the space where the community of Information Technology Directors of Latin American universities converge. It presents university the experiences, initiatives and knowledge, providing significant and unprecedented solutions in higher educational institutions specialized in ICT area.	2021. Date TBA.
21	Mexican International Conference on Artificial Intelligence	MICAI is characterized by Springer as premier conference in Artificial Intelligence. It is a high-level peer-reviewed international conference covering all areas of Artificial Intelligence, traditionally held in Mexico. The conference is organized by the Mexican Society for Artificial Intelligence (SMIA). The scientific program includes keynote lectures, paper presentations, tutorials, panels and workshops.	2021. TBA.
22	Congreso Mexicano de Inteligencia Artificial (COMIA)	COMIA is a high-level peer-reviewed conference covering all areas of Artificial Intelligence. The conference is organized by the Mexican Society for Artificial Intelligence (SMIA). The scientific program includes keynote lectures, paper presentations, tutorials, panels and workshops.	2021. TBA.
23	5th World Conference on Women	Led by the ALL Ladies League (ALL) and Women Economic Forum (WEF), the largest multinational networks of women entrepreneurs and leaders worldwide, Mission Million aims to have a MILLION sisters and supporters participate in what would be a 5 th World Forum on Women, in 2022, in India – a milestone moment to mark our mega global network of Sisters Beyond Borders.	2022. Date TBA.

3.2 Content Production for Communication Purposes

Given that GENDER STI is a Research and Innovation Action, the content to be produced for communication purposes will focus on the project overview and its planned research activities. It is important to highlight that the content for communication will be different than the content for dissemination, which has been described below in 4.2.

The communication content will be customized according to target group, purpose, communication channel and the specific moment in time, among others. Content will include, but is not limited to, the following topics:

- **GENDER STI project overview:** Content produced along this editorial line will include project objectives, scope, planned activities and synergies with other EU-funded projects and ERA working groups. This content will raise GENDER STI's profile, build momentum and create an image of an active project.
- **Promotion of GENDER STI Co-Design Lab workshops:** Content focused on the promotion of the Co-Design Labs will also be used to build momentum, gather possible workshops participants and form relevant connections with key members of the scientific and technological communities.
- **Promotion of final project event:** Content focused on promoting a final conference to present the GENDER STI results and recommendations. Like the promotion of the Co-Design Labs, the announcement and promotion of project events informs stakeholders that the project is active.

3.3 Communication materials

Communication materials are an important part of the project's strategy. These materials will support the project's promotional and multiplier activities as well as inform stakeholders on important project updates. The following are the communication materials that have been created thus far. Nonetheless, more materials will be created throughout the project's lifetime.

Logo

The GENDER STI logo was based on a computer motherboard. In this case, each of the three nodes represent key areas of the project's mission: science, technology and innovation. They're facing outwards and in different directions because the consortium is international and spread across four continents; the idea is that these nodes will reach far and beyond their possibilities. In a way, it can be compared to how the GENDER STI consortium views the role of women in STI. Our consortium firmly believes that women have the potential to break glass ceilings and use their knowledge in STI to make the world and society a better place.

The colors, purple and turquoise, were chosen out of a desire to make the project visually appealing to all and avoid traditional colors such as pink and dark blue.

Press Release

GENDER STI published a press release about the project's launch on its website. The press release laid out the project's research focus and explained its importance during the covid-19 era, which is threatening gains in the advancement of women worldwide.²

The complete press release can be seen in Annex 1.

Project Presentation

The consortium has prepared a visually impactful presentation that provides a breakdown of GENDER STI, its activities and its goals for project partners. Partners will be able to use the presentation to introduce the project at third-party events and networking activities, among others.

Excerpts from the project presentation can be seen in Annex 2.

² European Commission, High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy. (2020). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: EU Gender Action Plan (GAP) III – An Ambitious Agenda for Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in EU External Action*. (Final ed.) https://ec.europa.eu/international-partnerships/system/files/join-2020-17-final_en.pdf

4 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

Similar to the communication plan, GENDER STI's dissemination plan is based on three pillars: communication as groundwork for dissemination, dissemination to target audiences, and dissemination campaigns for high-impact channels. It is designed to work in perfect synergy with the project's communication plan.

Communication as groundwork for dissemination: GENDER STI will focus on communication activities during the first year of the project in order to lay the groundwork for the successful dissemination of scientific publishable results in year two. Executing dissemination activities in year two ensures that target audiences are familiar with GENDER STI and its scope, thereby increasing their receptiveness to receiving project results.

Disseminate to key target audiences: The second phase of GENDER STI's dissemination plan begins in year two at the moment when the project publishes its first interim results. GENDER STI will begin to launch targeted email campaigns to key stakeholders in the project's target audience groups. In addition, interim results will be presented to the project's target audiences in conferences and events.

Launch dissemination campaign in high-impact channels: The final phase of dissemination uses the groundwork and momentum developed during the first and second year of the project to begin dissemination of project results in relevant scientific and industry publications. These publications will allow the project to gain authority and successfully transfer knowledge to key target audiences. This phase will also include a final project event where the consortium can present the final results and lessons learned.

4.1 Dissemination Channels

The following are the main dissemination channels that will be used to transfer knowledge, tools and results to key stakeholder groups. Some of these channels are also used in communication, which is natural in our online world. However, channels used for dissemination purposes will focus on transferring project generated knowledge and results.

4.1.1 Email marketing platform

GENDER STI will leverage MailChimp, an email marketing platform, to create targeted dissemination campaigns, e.g., newsletters, for each of GENDER STI's target groups.

4.1.2 Social media and website

The GENDER STI social media channels and website will also be used for dissemination purposes. These mediums will be used to disseminate curated content and research results to key stakeholders involved in projects and initiatives related to gender equality in STI.

4.1.3 Gender STI Community of Practice

After completing the project's Co-Design Labs, core members in the Gender STI Community of Practice that participate in the lab become ambassadors that promote gender equality in STI dialogues with third countries using the skills acquired in the Co-Design Labs.

4.1.4 Scientific publications

Specific research publications will serve as channels that will delivering project results to the professional scientific community. Examples of such research publications include the *International Journal of Gender, Science and Technology*, *The Lancet Issue on Advancing Women in Science, Medicine and Global Health*, *the International Conference on Gender Research*, *the Conference on Gender IT*, *the Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, *the Interdisciplinary Conference on the Relations of Humans, Machines and Gender*, *the European Conference on Gender Equality & YOU*, *the European Conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education*, *the Annual Conference of the Gender Studies Association of Austria*, *the Journal of Gender and Ciencia Hoy*, among others.

4.1.5 Project events

The GENDER STI Co-Design Lab workshops and final conference will be used to directly disseminate project results to a carefully curated list of guests that are most likely to be interested in the project's research. These events will also be used to gather feedback that will contribute to and shape future project actions.

4.2 Content Production for Dissemination Purposes

The content to be produced for dissemination purposes will focus on project research results in order to produce engaging material to transfer knowledge that can be exploited by relevant stakeholders, such as the mapping on gender equality. In addition, content for dissemination will also focus on tools and mechanisms created by GENDER STI, such as the repository of multilateral and bilateral agreements in STI, the Community of Practice and the European Observatory on Gender in STI. The content and tools will be customized according to target group, purpose, dissemination channels and the specific moment in time, among others. Content and tools will include, but are not limited to, the following:

- **Survey report on gender equality implementation in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements.** This report will detail the results of the survey, which aims to provide insights from key actors in MS, AC and selected third countries about their perceptions on the implementation of gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements.
- **Mapping of gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements:** This report will provide the analysis of the present status of gender equality in formal bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI between MS and AC and selected third countries, as well as in the implementation activities and in the promotion of gender in international dialogues and cooperation.
- **Repository of multilateral and bilateral agreements in STI:** This tool will present the publicly available agreements analyzed by the project. The repository will be accessible to all interested in gender equality issues in STI on the project website.
- **Gender equality solutions and prototypes developed in Co-Design Labs:** As part of GENDER STI's Co-Design Labs, participants will develop solutions and prototypes that can be used to promote gender equality in

careers, gender equality in decision making and gender quality in R&I content. Solutions will also address how to integrate the gender perspective in STI dialogues with third countries. These solutions will be documented and shared as easy-to-read content on the project's website and social media channels.

- **European Observatory on Gender in STI:** This breakthrough, first of its kind tool in the EU will provide a centralized hub for all available knowledge on gender equality in STI dialogues with third countries. It will incorporate all materials analyzed and knowledge generated by the project.
- **Policy briefs on GENDER STI project results:** Content will be concise and readable and will focus on the GENDER STI results. Content could include, and is not limited to, the comparative analysis and benchmarking on gender equality in STI agreements with third countries, expert insights on gender equality generated by the Co-Design Lab workshops and the development of the European Observatory on Gender in STI. These deliverables aim to support the Commission in monitoring project achievements and impact as well as provide knowledge to support potential policy recommendations.
- **Policy recommendations:** Content will focus on policy recommendations the GENDER STI project will develop for key players like the EC, national MS authorities, third country partners' national authorities and funding agencies, among others. The recommendations are meant to serve as a reference for decision makers and enhance the integration of gender equality objectives in STI dialogues with third countries.

5 ESTIMATED EXECUTION TIMELINE

The following is an estimated execution timeline of GENDER STI's communication and dissemination activities. Like the Communication and Dissemination Plan itself, the timeline is fluid and can be modified as required by the project.

5.1 Communication Estimated Timeline

Year 1: GENDER STI launch and connection to key target audiences											
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
GENDER STI project launch. Creation of website and custom social media channels.			Present GENDER STI to other projects on gender equality in STI. Reinforce relationships with active projects and ERA-related groups.			Introduction of GENDER STI scope and objectives to partners' professional and institutional networks.			Promote Co-Design Labs and Community of Practice in EU and selected third countries.		
Year 2: Build momentum with project results											
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Promote first results on GENDER STI website and social media channels.			Publish results on partners' institutional websites and social media networks. Promote dissemination of results at third-party events.			Promote GENDER STI Co-Design Lab outcomes as well as interim project results on website, social media and partner channels.			Promote Co-Design Labs, Community of Practice and GENDER STI's next research steps.		
Year 3: Cascade results to ensure maximum reach											
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Contact specialized and generalized media about interim project results. Promote European Observatory on Gender in STI.			Launch email, social media and web campaign promoting the publication of project results. Promote Observatory.			Launch email, social media and web campaign promoting the final project event. Promote Observatory.			Promote recommendations and Observatory.		

5.2 Dissemination Estimated Timeline

Year 1: Use communication to lay groundwork for dissemination											
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Communication activities.											
Year 2: Begin dissemination to key target audiences											
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Launch targeted email campaigns with interim project results to GENDER STI's list of key stakeholders.			Present interim results at project events as well as third-party events.			Present interim results project events as well as third-party events.			Launch targeted email campaign to collect feedback on interim results and create engagement with the project.		
Year 3: Launch targeted dissemination campaign in high-impact channels											
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Continue to disseminate interim results, as well as the recently launched European Observatory on Gender in STI, at third-party events and announce that results will be presented soon.			Send results to targeted scientific and industry publications likely to be read by key stakeholder groups. Send results to GENDER STI's identified targeted audiences using established channels.			Publish results in targeted scientific and industry publications likely to be read by key stakeholder groups. Send results to GENDER STI's identified target audiences using established channels.			Host final project event and present results and publications to a curated list of the project's target audiences.		

6 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

In order to ensure that the GENDER STI Communication and Dissemination Plan is maximizing the project's impact and increasing its reach, we will measure the plan's efficiency with quantitative and qualitative indicators. Should significant deviation occur, e.g., a failure to achieve objectives set in three or more indicators, the consortium will adapt the plan and adopt the necessary measures to get the project back on track.

Nonetheless, the plan is a living document, and will be continuously adapted and optimized to meet the project's needs.

Quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) refer to those that can be measured with analytics tools, e.g., website visits, and other means of numerical measurement. Meanwhile, qualitative KPIs are those that cannot be easily measured through numerical means. An example of this includes community engagement and responses to content.

Given that some channels are used in both the communication and dissemination strategies, some indicators will be included in both communication and dissemination.

6.1 Communication KPIs

KPIs for the project's communication aim to ensure the project, as well as the reach of European R&I in general, is promoted to the project's key stakeholders. The communication actions will lay the groundwork for the project's dissemination actions by informing stakeholders of its goals and research questions.

6.1.1 Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
Availability of GENDER STI website	Website online 24/7	Website online 24/7
Website visits	3,000 visits	6,000 visits
Social media followers	Twitter: 300 Facebook: 100 LinkedIn: 50	Twitter: 600 Facebook: 200 LinkedIn: 100
Project news articles on website	30 articles.	60 articles.
Third-Party events attended by project partners	At least 20 events.	At least 60 events.
Number of presentations about the project at third-party events	At least 10 presentations.	At least 20 presentations.
Promotional actions carried out by partners on their online channels	At least 10 actions.	At least 20 actions.
Newsletters	At least one each quarter.	At least two each quarter.

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
Participate in joint meetings of bi-regional dialogues between EU and third countries.	-	At least one meeting for each region partner of the project (Latin America, Asia, Africa and North America).
Attendees to project Co-Design Labs	At least 50.	At least 150.

*Note: The totals in reporting period 2 are cumulative.

6.1.2 Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions on online channels.	Positive mentions on online channels and links to its digital materials.
Proactive online community	Community that engages with the project's content.	Community that engages with the project's content and promotes it.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.	An increase in the project's contributions to other actions.

*Note: The totals in reporting 2 are cumulative.

6.2 Dissemination KPIs

The aim of dissemination is to transfer project generated to knowledge to stakeholders that can benefit from it. Therefore, dissemination KPIs will focus on the transfer and engagement with project results.

6.2.1 Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
Number of attendees to Project Co-Design Labs	At least 50	At least 150
Email campaigns with project results	At least two	At least four
Number of citations of project results in online channels	10	30
Number of visits to project publications page	200	500
Number of visits to Observatory page	200	500
Publish papers on GENDER STI results in scientific journals	-	At least 5 different journals.
Number of policy briefs on GENDER STI	-	2

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
research findings and recommendations.		
Number of attendees to project final event	-	80-100

*Note: The totals in reporting period two are cumulative.

6.2.2 Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Reporting Period 2
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions of project results on online channels.	Positive mentions of project results on online channels and links to its digital materials.
Proactive online community	Scientific community that engages with project's results and adds to the conversation.	Scientific community that engages with project's results and adds to the conversation.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution, specifically project results, from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.	An increase in the project's contributions, specifically project results, to other actions.

ANNEX 1

Project Press Release

International EU-Funded Consortium Launches Project to Analyze the Gender Perspective in Science, Technology and Innovation

1 NOVEMBER 2020. MADRID, SPAIN – An international consortium of 16 countries launched the **Gender Equality in Science, Technology and Innovation in Bilateral and Multilateral Dialogues (GENDER STI)** research project today. The project is co-funded by Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

GENDER STI will analyze how gender equality matters are taken into consideration at different levels of international cooperation dialogues in the area of science, technology and innovation (STI). In particular, the project will work with 10 third countries from three continents and analyze bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI between EU Member States and these countries.

Institutions from the following countries are partners in the project: Canada, the U.S., Mexico, Brazil, Chile, Argentina, South Africa, India, South Korea, and China. All of the third countries involved in GENDER STI have a long-standing history of cooperation with Europe in the area of STI.

The project is coordinated by Spain. Other EU partners from Finland, Portugal, Austria, France and Italy also play key roles in GENDER STI.

The project is scheduled to last three years and is part of Horizon 2020's Science with and for Society (SwafS) program.

In addition to studying the current state of gender in STI dialogues, GENDER STI will co-design solutions for common challenges, such as gender equality in careers and gender balance in decision-making, related to gender equality in STI. To accomplish this, it will use a design thinking process to engage with relevant stakeholders in the EU and the third countries.

Yolanda Ursa, GENDER STI scientific coordinator and Innovation Management Director of Inmark Europa, expressed excitement about the start of the project and stressed the importance of studying gender equality in STI in the covid-19 era.

“We are seeing an unprecedented amount of international cooperation in science as researchers around the world partner together to find effective treatments and

vaccines for covid-19,” Ursa said. “During these critical times, it is important to ensure that women are given opportunities to participate in this international research and identify the barriers that might prevent them from doing so.”

Furthermore, GENDER STI will launch the European Observatory on Gender in STI. The observatory, the first of its kind in Europe, will serve as a hub for gender equality in STI dialogues, incorporating all current knowledge on the subject and housing the materials developed by the project.

-- Ends --

For more information, please contact:

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ANNEX 2

Excerpts from the Project's Presentation

Project Scope

- **Type of action:** Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
- **Call:** H2020-SwafS-2019-1
- **Topic:** SwafS-12-2019 The gender perspective of science, technology and innovation (STI) in dialogue with third countries
- **Duration:** 3 years
- **Start date:** 1 November 2020

Co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation Programme.

Objectives

- Over the next three years, GENDER STI will work to carry out the following objectives.
- Provide a **mapping** of how gender equality is taken into account and promoted in bilateral and multilateral agreements in the STI area between the EU MS and AC and the 10 selected third countries.
- Perform a **comparative analysis and benchmarking** on gender equality in STI agreements with selected third countries.
- Build on the work done by the ERA related groups in charge of gender equality and **international cooperation** as well as EU funded projects.
- Design and implement a series of **Co-Design Lab workshops** in the EU and selected third countries.
- Formulate **recommendations** to enhance the integration of gender equality objectives in STI dialogues between Europe and third countries.
- Increase **visibility of GENDER STI outcomes** and maximize the impact of the project.

Co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation Programme.

